

GENERATIVE MODEL-DRIVEN DESIGN OF LONG DISCONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES FOR TARGETED MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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Keywords: Carbon fiber, Discontinuous reinforcement, Finite element analysis (FEA), Microstructure, Numerical analysis, Mechanical properties, Computational modelling

ABSTRACT

This study presents a two-stage inverse-design framework for discontinuous carbon-fiber composites that generates variable-stiffness structures by linking macro-scale structural requirements with region-specific microstructural design. A genetic algorithm (GA) was used to determine macro-scale region-specific stiffness targets for a quarter-cornerhole geometry, reducing maximum local longitudinal S_{11} stress by 25% relative to a uniform stiffness baseline in which all fibers are aligned parallel to the applied load, while maintaining a longitudinal specimen stiffness above 30 GPa. Next, an Abaqus FEA pipeline generated a dataset of two-dimensional representative volume elements (RVEs) varying fiber volume fraction, length, width, orientation, and gap to characterize microstructural stiffness responses. Finally, a conditional GAN (cGAN), trained on this RVE dataset, inversely mapped the GA-derived stiffness targets to manufacturable microstructural parameters. FEA validation confirmed that the cGAN generated microstructures met the stiffness targets within 1 GPa and enabled a 13% reduction in average fiber volume fraction without compromising performance. This GA and cGAN workflow enable region-by-region generation of fiber microstructures that achieve target stiffness distributions and provides a scalable method for extending inverse design to three dimensional composite architectures and physical validation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Designing composite materials that simultaneously meet requirements for stiffness, strength, and geometry remains a critical challenge in aerospace and automotive applications. In such domains, precise control over material properties is essential to ensure structural performance under spatial and loading constraints [1]. Traditional composite design approaches have largely relied on empirically derived design rules from extensive experimental coupon testing regimes [2]. Due to their robust and conservative nature, such methods create initial designs where further optimization is constrained. Forward design using finite element analysis (FEA) simulations is limited due to computational cost, which increases significantly for nonlinear materials or complex geometries, making repeated simulation over large design spaces impractical [3]. Thus, FEA is generally used at later design stages to produce accurate assessments of mechanical behavior for predefined configurations of fibers and matrix systems [4]. To improve initial design, simple physics-based analytical models such as the rule of mixtures and Halpin–Tsai equations have been employed to estimate effective properties [5,6], however the models inherently break down for more complex design scenarios. While these different design methods have proven valuable, they are either too restrictive, too computationally expensive, or too inaccurate for the full complex inverse design problem of determining optimal material configurations that satisfy specific performance targets for realistic design parts [7].

To address these limitations, machine learning-based inverse design strategies have been introduced providing scope for improved accuracy and speed of computation [8]. Among them, generative modeling approaches offer a promising direction by directly constructing material configurations conditioned on target mechanical properties. Unlike regression-based surrogate models or traditional optimization, which improve existing designs within fixed spaces, generative models synthesize new designs that reflect desired physical behaviors. Generative adversarial networks (GANs) and other deep generative architectures such as variational autoencoders and conditional U-Nets have been applied in materials science to accelerate design workflows and reduce reliance on high-resolution simulations [9,10]. When trained on representative volume element (RVE) FEA datasets paired with mechanical response labels, these models can generate material structures aligned with specified performance metrics [3].

This study proposes a generative modeling framework for the inverse design of discontinuous fiber reinforced composites (DFRCs). Leveraging a FEA dataset of systematically varied RVE configurations and their corresponding stiffness values for training [11], the proposed approach aims to generate composite designs that satisfy user-defined mechanical targets [12]. This framework offers a scalable and efficient alternative to conventional FEA-based methods and supports performance-driven composite design.

2 RELATED WORKS

2.1 Surrogate modeling approaches in composite design

To mitigate the computational cost associated with simulation-based composite design, surrogate models trained on numerical results have been extensively employed. Techniques such as linear regression, polynomial response surfaces, and Gaussian process (GP) regression have been used to approximate mechanical responses within a reduced design space using a limited set of simulation samples [13]. These models enable rapid evaluation and are effective in capturing low-order design trends. However, their predictive accuracy diminishes significantly in high-dimensional or strongly nonlinear design spaces characteristic of complex composite systems. In response to these limitations, physics-informed machine learning (PIML) methods have been proposed to enhance the extrapolation and generalization capability of surrogate models [14]. These methods incorporate governing physical laws either as soft constraints in the loss function or via hybrid inputs combining simulation results and domain knowledge. While promising, PIML approaches often demand substantial training data and still struggle when operating beyond the distribution of the original training set [15]. Moreover, most surrogate modeling techniques are inherently constructed for forward prediction. As such, they are not directly suited for inverse design tasks, where the goal is to generate material configurations that achieve specified property targets or satisfy performance criteria under design constraints.

2.2 Deep generative modeling for inverse material design

Generative approaches have recently emerged as effective tools for inverse design, particularly in materials science domains characterized by high-dimensional, nonlinear, and non-convex design spaces. While generative adversarial networks (GANs) are widely studied, other frameworks such as variational autoencoders (VAEs), conditional U-Nets, and diffusion models have also demonstrated promising results in structural and microstructural synthesis [16, 17]. VAEs enable latent encoding of geometric and material features, facilitating efficient sampling and interpolation across the design space. Such models have been used to generate microstructure configurations aligned with target properties through structure–property mapping in the latent space [18]. Similarly, U-Net–based generative models have proven effective in pixel-wise or voxel-wise material structure prediction when conditioned on optimization results or segmentation masks [19]. More recently, diffusion models have been explored for the generation of high-resolution material topologies under physics-guided constraints. These models can produce diverse and stable outputs and can be conditioned on properties such as stiffness, porosity, or thermal conductivity during the iterative denoising process [20]. Despite their efficiency, generative models often require additional post-processing or constraints to ensure physical validity and manufacturability of the generated designs.

2.3 Inverse design in composite materials

Due to the inherent anisotropy and microstructural complexity of composite materials, inverse design requires handling diverse factors such as fiber orientation, stacking sequences, and matrix behavior. Several studies have adapted generative approaches specifically for composites by incorporating structure–property datasets based on RVEs [8]. These models learn latent design spaces where interpolation or sampling can yield new configurations aligned with mechanical targets. Such data-driven frameworks have shown particular promise for discontinuous fiber-reinforced composites, extending inverse design capability to discontinuous fiber reinforced composites (DFRCs) [19].

3 METHODOLOGY

A two-stage framework integrating macro-scale structural optimization with micro-scale inverse material design is presented. First, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) identifies the optimal distribution of target mechanical properties for distinct regions within a structure to meet specified global performance criteria, such as stiffness and stress constraints. Second, the optimized regional properties are used to inversely generate manufacturable microstructural parameters. This inverse design process utilizes a conditional Generative Adversarial Network (cGAN) trained on a dataset of Representative Volume Elements (RVEs) obtained via finite element simulations. This integrated approach ensures that macro-scale structural requirements are practically translated into micro-scale design parameters, enabling efficient material usage with targeted performance.

3.1 Macro-scale structural optimization using GA

In this study, a GA was employed to optimize the discrete fiber composite material distribution of a quarter-cornerhole specimen loaded in uniaxial tension, see Figure 1. The objective of the GA optimization was twofold: (a) minimize the maximum local longitudinal stress, $S_{11,MAX}$, while (b) maintaining a minimum effective specimen longitudinal Young's modulus, $E_{11,SP}$, of 30 GPa. The structural domain was discretized into four distinct regions, and each region was assigned a set of orthotropic material properties as design variables. Specifically, directional Young's moduli (E_{11} , E_{22}), in-plane Poisson's ratio (ν_{12}), and shear modulus (G_{12}) were allowed to vary in accordance with the range of material configurations in the RVE dataset, as detailed in Section 3.3 and summarized in Table 1. The GA optimization procedure, as illustrated in Figure 1, began with an initial population comprising 16 randomly generated sets of these material properties within the ranges [10, 30] GPa (E_{11}) and [1, 20] GPa (E_{22} , G_{12}). Each candidate solution (individual) within the population was evaluated through FEA using Abaqus, providing fitness scores based on the primary structural optimization goal of minimizing $S_{11,MAX}$ while only being accepted for further generations if they achieve the minimum effective specimen stiffness target, $E_{11,SP}^T$. Subsequently, genetic operators including selection, crossover, and mutation were applied iteratively to generate improved populations. The optimization loop continued until satisfaction of convergence criteria by either (i) change of the lowest found minimum of maximum local stress, $\Delta S_{11,MAX}^{min}(G) \leq$ minimum improvement value, MIV, of 1×10^{-3} (ii) number of iterations, G , reaches the maximum value, N , of 30. The outcome of the GA optimization was a set of optimal target mechanical properties defined for each region, reducing maximum stress concentrations and maintaining structural integrity. These optimized regional properties served as inputs for the subsequent micro-scale inverse design step, explained in Section 3.3, using the pre-trained cGAN model, explained in Section 3.2.

Figure 1: Architecture of genetic algorithm operators within each generation.

3.2 RVE dataset for cGAN model

To train the proposed conditional generative model for inverse design, a dataset was constructed using FEA of DFRC structures. Each data sample corresponds to a two-dimensional RVE, modeled as a square domain containing same direction fibers embedded in a continuous matrix. The geometrical and material configurations of the fibers were systematically varied to produce a wide range of mechanical responses under in-plane loading. The key design parameters considered during RVE generation include fiber gap, volume fraction, fiber length and width, orientation angle, and the elastic moduli of the fiber and matrix materials. These parameters were selected based on their known influence on in-plane stiffness characteristics of unidirectional composite plies. A subset of 200 RVE configurations was sampled from the full-factorial parameter space to ensure representative coverage across all key design variables. The parameter definitions and their corresponding ranges are summarized in Table 1.

Parameter		Range
Fiber gap (f_g)	[mm]	0.1-3.0
Volume fraction (V_f)	–	0.1-0.6
Fiber length (f_l)	[mm]	5-25
Fiber width (f_w)	[μ m]	0.5-5
Fiber orientation (θ_f)	[$^\circ$]	0-90
Fiber Young's modulus (E_{11})	[GPa]	231
Fiber Young's modulus (E_{22})	[GPa]	10
Fiber Young's modulus (G_{12})	[GPa]	5
Fiber Poisson's ratio (ν_{12})	–	0.3
Matrix Young's modulus (E_m)	[GPa]	5
Fiber Poisson's ratio (ν_m)	–	0.3

Table 1: Parameter ranges and increments used for generating the RVE dataset

For each configuration, static finite element simulations were conducted using Abaqus to evaluate the homogenized in-plane elastic properties, including directional Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios. The geometry generation, meshing, simulation, and data extraction were implemented in a unified workflow to ensure consistency across all samples. The RVE microstructures were generated as 2D

images with fiber regions shown in yellow and matrix regions in teal. Figure 2 (a) highlights the key geometric parameters: fiber width, fiber gap, and fiber orientation. The final dataset consists of approximately 200 samples, each comprising a paired input–output tuple: a binary microstructure image and the corresponding scalar stiffness value. This dataset serves as the training foundation for the cGAN. Figure 2 (b) presents representative the statistical distributions of the dataset parameters and mechanical responses obtained by randomly sampling values within the ranges specified in Table 1.

Figure 2: (a) Samples RVE structure with fiber width, gap and orientation (b) Distributions of dataset variables: volume fraction, fiber orientation, and the corresponding stiffness values E_{11} and E_{22}

3.3 Micro-scale inverse design via cGAN

A cGAN was synthesized to predict the microstructural parameters of DFRC structures that satisfy user-defined stiffness targets. The model is based on the standard cGAN formulation, where both the generator G and discriminator D receive a condition vector c to guide the generation process. In this implementation, the condition vector consisted of the raw stiffness target and the desired loading direction. This structure allows the model to generate designs tailored to specific mechanical responses along the specified axis. The generator takes as input a concatenated vector $[z, c]$, where z is a latent noise vector sampled from a standard Gaussian distribution. The output is a vector of RVE design parameters, including fiber volume fraction, fiber orientation, fiber length, fiber width and fiber gap. These parameters define a composite structure that is expected to achieve the desired stiffness when evaluated under the given loading condition.

The discriminator is trained to distinguish between real (dataset-derived) and fake (generated) RVE configurations, conditioned on the same stiffness and direction input c . This enforces conditional realism in the generated structures. The training process employs adversarial loss, feature matching regularization, and label smoothing to stabilize convergence and improve the fidelity of the generated samples. An overview of the proposed generative design pipeline is illustrated in Figure 3. After training the generator G and discriminator D together, the generator G is used to predict parameters that are likely to result in the real vector c .

Figure 3: Architecture of the cGAN for inverse design of composite microstructures.

To quantitatively validate the generator output, a separate property prediction model is incorporated into the framework. Predictor is a fully connected neural network trained on the simulation-based dataset. It takes the generated RVE design parameters as input and estimates the corresponding equivalent stiffness. The predicted value is compared with the original target to assess inverse design accuracy and guide model refinement.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Macro-scale optimization results

Macro-scale optimization was evaluated on a quarter-cornerhole specimen results using the GA-based method outlined in Section 3.1. A quarter-cornerhole specimen with four distinct stiffness regions was chosen as the representative geometry (Figure 4). The objective of the GA optimization was twofold: (a) maintain a minimum global Young's modulus of 30 GPa, and (b) minimize the maximum S_{11} stress under uniaxial tension. The GA optimization began from randomly generated initial stiffness values within the ranges of [10, 30] GPa (E_{11}) and [1, 20] GPa (E_{22} , G_{12}), running for 30 generations with a population size of 16. Fitness evaluation involved running Abaqus finite element analyses to calculate effective stiffness and maximum S_{11} stress for each candidate. Results from the optimization demonstrate that region-wise tailored stiffness values significantly reduce local stress concentrations compared to a baseline uniform stiffness distribution. Specifically, the optimized design achieved a maximum stress reduction of approximately 25%, lowering the peak stress from 391 MPa to 289 MPa.

Figure 4: Von Mises stress contours for the quarter-cornerhole specimen under uniaxial tension: (a)

Baseline design with a uniform Young's modulus of 30 GPa (b) GA-optimized stiffness distribution reduces the maximum S_{11}

Furthermore, Figure 4 compares baseline and optimized designs. With fiber length fixed at 25 mm, the optimized design showed a reduction in the average fiber volume fraction from 0.39 (baseline) to 0.34, representing about a 12.8% material saving while still satisfying stiffness constraints. This result highlights the effectiveness of the proposed GA optimization in achieving both structural performance and material efficiency, which is beneficial for manufacturing.

4.2 Micro-scale inverse design results

Performance of the cGAN-based inverse design method described in Section 3.2 was evaluated. Experiments were conducted on simplified square-shaped RVEs. The trained cGAN model generated RVE design parameters fiber volume fraction (V_f), orientation angle (θ_f), fiber gap (f_g), fiber width (f_w), and fiber length (f_l) based on user-defined stiffness targets and loading directions (either E_{11} or E_{22}). Representative RVE designs obtained from the cGAN model and corresponding stiffness results computed via Abaqus simulations are summarized in Table 2.

	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
Target	10 Gpa (E_{11})		4 Gpa (E_{22})	
	$V_f = 0.17, \theta_f = 0^\circ,$	$V_f = 0.24, \theta_f = 15^\circ,$	$V_f = 0.44, \theta_f = 37^\circ,$	$V_f = 0.38, \theta_f = 28^\circ,$
Design parameters	$f_l = 19.79 \text{ mm},$ $f_g = 2.5 \text{ mm},$ $f_w = 2.06 \mu\text{m}$	$f_l = 21.71 \text{ mm},$ $f_g = 0.83 \text{ mm},$ $f_w = 3.0 \mu\text{m}$	$f_l = 10.00 \text{ mm},$ $f_g = 0.79 \text{ mm},$ $f_w = 1.51 \mu\text{m}$	$f_l = 8.29 \text{ mm},$ $f_g = 0.69 \text{ mm},$ $f_w = 1.38 \mu\text{m}$
Abaqus results (GPa)	9.86	9.96	4.47	4.04

Table 2: Representative RVE designs for target stiffness values, showing design parameters and the corresponding effective modulus obtained from Abaqus FEA.

For a 10 GPa E_{11} target, generated designs exhibited V_f values of 0.17, 0.24, and 0.44, producing moduli of 9.86 GPa, 9.96 GPa, and 10.04 GPa, respectively. For a 4 GPa E_{22} target, designs with V_f of 0.38 and 0.44 yielded 4.04 GPa and 4.47 GPa. The results illustrate that multiple distinct RVE configurations can satisfy the same stiffness target. Figure 5 further compares target stiffness values, Abaqus-computed stiffness, and predicted stiffness from the trained neural network predictor. The cGAN-generated designs accurately matched the target stiffness values, with a mean absolute error (MAE) of 0.78 GPa for E_{11} and 0.62 GPa for E_{22} .

Figure 5: Comparison of target stiffness inputs, Abaqus-computed results, and cGAN-based inverse design predictions for three test cases

4.3 Discussions

This study presented a two-stage inverse-design framework integrating macro-scale structural optimization using a GA and micro-scale inverse design using a cGAN. The results indicate that this combined approach effectively achieves region-specific stiffness targets while significantly reducing maximum stress concentrations compared to baseline uniform stiffness distributions. Specifically, the two-stage optimization process resulted in a reduction of approximately 25% in maximum stress and approximately 13% material savings through optimized fiber configurations. By automating the workflow between region-wise property optimization (GA) and microstructure generation (cGAN).

However, the current approach has several limitations that should be addressed in future research. The present RVE dataset was limited to two-dimensional microstructures; extending the data set and inverse-design space to 3D laminated regions is necessary for laminated composite part design. Practical considerations such as fiber misalignment, resin flow during manufacturing, and thermal residual stresses introduced during additive manufacturing, must be systematically investigated, as these factors critically affect the mechanical performance of composite structures. Extending the dataset to three-dimensional RVEs for a single lamina accounting for these manufacturing effects, and including experimental validation data, would enhance the model's predictive capability and broaden its practical application. This study was conducted on a simplified quarter-cornerhole geometry under uniaxial loading conditions; real-world structural components typically involve more complex geometries, curved surfaces and multi-axial loading conditions. Future research should focus on adapting and validating this inverse-design framework for complex three-dimensional geometries under realistic operational loading scenarios. Lastly, for practical deployment in additive manufacturing processes, key challenges such as printer resolution limitations, accuracy in fiber placement, and void formation must be addressed. Incorporating these manufacturing constraints into the inverse-design process will be critical to ensuring that optimized designs can be reliably and efficiently realized in practice.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This research introduced a two-stage inverse-design framework combining macro-scale structural optimization using a GA and micro-scale material design through a conditional Generative Adversarial Network cGAN. The proposed GA-cGAN framework successfully prescribed manufacturable fiber microstructure parameters that satisfied region-specific stiffness requirements while achieving up to 25% reduction in maximum stress compared to uniform-stiffness baselines. Additionally, optimized fiber configurations enabled approximately 13% material savings without compromising mechanical performance. Future studies will focus on extending the framework to fully three-dimensional microstructures, performing experimental validation of optimized designs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by Korea Institute for Advancement of Technology (KIAT) grant funded by the Korea Government (MOTIE) (RS-2024-00436124, Human Resource Development Program for Industrial Innovation (Global))

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